

THE SIGNIFICANCE OF ENGLISH GRAMMAR FOR ESL TEACHERS

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Anotatsiya. Kommunikativ tilni o'rgatishning hozirgi davrida, ba'zi til o'qituvchilarining fikriga ko'ra, grammatika muloqot uchun haqiqatan ham muhim emasligini ta'kidlashadi, boshqa olimlar grammatika hali ham o'quvchilarning til tizimini rivojlantirishda asosiy rol o'ynashini tan olishadi. Oxirgi istiqbollari va turli tadqiqotlarga ko'ra, til o'rgatish va o'rganishda grammatik o'qitishni qanday samarali qo'llash mumkinligi ko'rib chiqilmoqda.

Tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatdiki, nafaqat grammatika qoidalari yoki tuzilmalari to'plami, balki grammatika bo'yicha bilimga ega bo'lish ham o'quvchilarga ingliz tilini o'rganish muvaffaqiyatini oshirishga yordam beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: grammatik tushunchalar, aloqa, lug'at, grammatika, poydevor, ESL, EFL, grammatika tuzilmalari va boshqalar.

Аннотация. В наши дни и в эпоху коммуникативного преподавания языка, по мнению некоторых учителей языка, грамматика не очень важна для общения, другие ученые признают, что грамматика по-прежнему играет главную роль в развитии языковой системы учащихся. С учетом последних взглядов и различных исследований проводится изучение того, как эффективно применять обучение грамматике в преподавании и изучении языка.

Исследования показали, что не только набор правил или структур грамматики, но и знание грамматики могут помочь учащимся улучшить свой прогресс в обучении английскому языку.

Ключевые слова: грамматические понятия, общение, лексика, грамматика, основа, ESL, EFL, структуры грамматики и др.

Annotation. In this day and age of communicative language teaching, according to some language teachers inform that grammar is not really important for communication, other scientists admit that grammar still plays a main role in developing the language system of learners. From the recent perspectives and different researches, how to effectively apply grammar instruction in language teaching and learning is conducted.

The studies showed that not only a set of rules or structures of grammar but also having knowledge of grammar can support learners to amplify their EFL learning progress.

Keywords: grammatical concepts, communication, vocabulary, grammar, foundation, ESL, EFL, structures of grammar and etc.

INTRODUCTION

It is a fact that grammar is the structure and meaning system of language and all languages have their own grammar. In the current communicative language teaching, a number of language learners and some native teachers consider that learning grammar when learning English language is not essential any longer. Grammar places the important role of learning and teaching English languages as well. In addition, English grammar is so necessary for the teachers to combine grammar into other language skills and to inspire learners about benefits of learning grammar.

RESEARCH METHODS

Grammar can be generally defined as “a knowledge of what words can go where and what form these words should take” ¹(Harmer, 2015, p. 22). Following that, according to some vital factors of grammar, learners of English should pay attention to which requires sentences and clauses, verbs, nouns and noun phrases, adverbs and adjectives. It is concerned that teachers teach grammar depending on goals of the language program, learners’ capacity, ages, level of language proficiency and learning styles. According to the practice, it can be difficult to some teachers to make grammar lessons become lively and exciting. Therefore, the teaching grammar in traditional ways causes to make a lesson inactive and is defined as outdated method of language teaching and learning progression.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Grammar is a rule of making meaning. “Grammar is an analysis of the structure of a language, either as encountered in a corpus of speech or writing (a performance grammar) or as predictive of a speaker's knowledge (a competence grammar)”.² (Nunan, 2001) Likewise, it is the description of a language, and it can help to understand how words and component parts combine to form sentences. People can communicate easily with others who speak the same language because they possibly know the grammar system of that language as well as the rules of making meaning. Teaching speaking skills in English does not show that student knows language that’s why teacher need to teach the learners how to transfer their knowledge of grammatical concepts from oral language to written language. After teaching grammar rules, learners can become more accurate when using a language because rules help students develop the habit of thinking logically and clearly. If learners do not learn grammar and using it in the speech, they cannot communicate and speak fluently with others. "Grammar is the structural foundation of our ability to express ourselves. The more we

¹ Harmer, J. (2015). *The Practice of English Language Teaching* (5th ed.). Essex, England: Pearson Education.

² Nunan, D. (2001). *Second Language Teaching & Learning*. USA: HEINLE& HEINLE PUBLISHERS.
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are aware of how it works, the more we can monitor the meaning and effectiveness of the way we and others use language. It can help foster precision, detect ambiguity, and exploit the richness of expression available in English."³ Without a doubt, our important words are able to become less powerful with grammar problems or our communication cannot be effective with bad grammar for that reason, grammar means the rules and regulations that ruled the spoken and written language. Besides that, English grammar comes with a lot of rules and it is very vital process for learners. If student knows grammar very well, he or she can write or speak in such a way that choice of words is understandable and follows the basic rules of sentence construction, punctuation and spelling as well. In learning English as a Second Language (ESL) or (EFL), it is a very important process for the teacher himself to have sufficient knowledge of grammar and to be able to teach it correctly to the students. In that case, in teaching language grammar is so important.

It is generally accepted that grammar is the foundation for communication. "The teaching of grammar is the teaching of the rules of grammar as part of language education. In the context of the second language instruction, the teaching of grammar is generally aimed at imparting the learners' knowledge and ability to use the language grammatically correctly".⁴ In fact, the correct English grammar does not matter only to teacher but also to all learners in order to improve the development of fluency. It can be easier for that person to know how to organize and express the ideas in their mind without difficulty even if a person has learned grammar. In addition, learning English grammar and using it correctly takes a lot of time and practice. It means that a teacher of English may spend her or his whole life for learning, repeating and teaching grammar. If a teacher does not know correctly use the grammar, he cannot teach the English as a Foreign language and four English language skills even. As we know, grammar and vocabulary are not language skills because they are language components

³ David Crystal, 2004.

⁴ Singh. V., D. (2008) Language Learning, Teaching and Testing A Companion. New Delhi: CUP.

which are important to the mastery of all skills so that we cannot use any language skill without using grammar and vocabulary. The success of students in language learning depends on the teacher's mastery of the grammar of the language and the ability how to able to teach the learners. "Grammar is the backbone of language and without it, the produced text, whether it is spoken or written, will be classified with many labels: broken, uneducated, incomprehensible or simply not belonging to the English language."⁵ In my view, native speakers can learn the language in a natural environment but learning language as a Foreign Language or Second Language can be acquired by systematic teaching programs in schools and higher languages. That's why teachers play very essential role to acquire the language.

However, through the importance of the language grammar many ESL teachers are used to teaching grammar separately from the four language skills. As a result, learners have a number of mistakes to make sentences out of the context, that's why; students have to internalize the grammar points through grammatical books. Consequently, it is clear that grammar remains popular and the Grammar Translation is still dominant in teaching approaches.

CONCLUSION

To sum up, learning and teaching grammar are very complicated processes and there is one way to improve it is to read more in English. Knowing and using English grammar correctly can give us great opportunity to understand English easier, enhance our language skills and work more effectively. Therefore, to have knowledge of English grammar is very necessary for a teacher of English as a Foreign Language and student as well.

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⁵ Ali Mansouri, 2017

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